

Antidiabetic Potential of *Azadirachta indica* Aqueous leaves Extract on Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Diabetes is a life threatening health issue that is becoming more prevalent and poses a great health problem and a colossal responsibility on global economy. Effective phytomedicine can serve as a good source for the management of diabetes and provide an effective economic growth. This study was carried out to evaluate the antidiabetic potential of aqueous leaves extract of *Azadirachta indica* on streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic Wistar rats. Diabetes was induced by a single intraperitoneal administration of 60 mg/kg of STZ. Thirty male rats were randomly distributed into 6 groups of 5 rats each. Normal and diabetic control groups received distilled water; diabetic rats were orally treated using gavage 100, 300 and 400 mg/kg of aqueous extract of *A. indica* and 5 mg/kg glibenclamide for 4 weeks. Fasting blood glucose was monitored weekly. Administration of 60 mg/kg of STZ resulted to significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in fasting blood glucose, TC, TG, LDL, urea and creatinine levels. SOD, CAT, GSH and HDL cholesterol levels were significantly reduced. Treatment with *A. indica* extract reversed the effect of STZ on above parameters. These findings indicated that aqueous leaves extract of *A. indica* is effective in the management of diabetes and could be considered as potential antidiabetic therapy

Keywords: Antioxidant, *Azadirachta indica*, diabetes, glibenclamide, streptozotocin.

1.0 Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a serious long term or chronic condition that results due to increased levels of blood glucose because of the body's inability to produce any or sufficient insulin or cannot properly utilize the insulin it has produced [1]. Diabetes can cause damage to many organs of the body if left unchecked over long time causing disability or life threatening health complications such as cardiovascular diseases (CVD), kidney damage (nephropathy), nerve damage (neuropathy), visual loss or blindness (retinopathy), etc, but if it is well managed, these serious complications can be delayed or even prevented [1].

Diabetes is among the top ten causes of mortality in the world; it accounts for about 4.9 million deaths per year in the world, with about 50% of the deaths occurring in persons under 60 years of age. About 612 billion dollars is spent on diabetes

worldwide representing 11% of the health expenditure world-wide [1]. It is estimated that 537 million people have diabetes [1] globally, and this number is projected to reach 643 million by 2030, and 783 million by 2045 [1]. The orthodox medical way of managing DM with oral hypoglycemic agents and insulin injection lacks adequacy and compliance, and is also costly. This exposes the patient to a high risk of long-term complications such as diabetic nephropathy.

The plant kingdom represents a rich store of organic compounds, many of which have been used for medicinal purposes and could serve as a lead for the development of novel agents [2]. These plants are found within our environment, they do not only provide humans with oxygen nor do they only serve as source of food chain, but are also reservoirs of phytochemicals for medicinal purposes [3], even though importance of most plants remains heavily unexplored due poor insight of their medicinal potentials [4].

Nowadays, due high demand and side effects of conventional medicines, many parts of the world started the use plants for the treatment and prevention of diseases [3]. The use of these plants and phytoconstituents may improve insulin secretion, delay the development of diabetic complications and may regulate the metabolic abnormalities through a variety of mechanisms [5]. *Azadirachta indica* (neem), life giving tree [2], divine tree [6] has been declared the tree of the 21st century by the United Nations [2], is the most versatile and useful medicinal plant ever found [7]. Moreover, the demand for herbal medicines is increasing day by day; thus, it is important to explore potential attenuator of diabetes from *Azadirachta indica* that will serve as an alternative to the conventional medical approach in the management of diabetic complications.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample Collection and Identification

The sample was collected intake-off Campus, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State, Nigeria and was taken same day for identification.

Plate 1: Leaves of *Azadirachta indica*

2.2 Sample Identification

The sample was identified at the Herbarium of Botany Unit of the Department of Biological Sciences Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Voucher number: FUDMA/PSB/00002 was given to the sample.

2.3 Sample Preparation

The sample was sorted and air dried under shade at room temperature for two weeks, it was grounded to powder. Distilled water 1000 ml was added to each 150 g of the powdered sample and

was soaked for 24 hours. It was filtered with muslin cloth followed by Whatman filter paper number 1 and the extract was collected and dried in oven at 60°C which was used for the analyses.

2.4 Experimental Animals

A total of thirty (30) male Wistar albino rats with average weight 152.73 g were purchased from the Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. They were maintained and housed in aluminum cages in the Animal house, Biochemistry section, Federal University Dutsin-Ma. They were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks before use. The animals were fed with standard diet and water *ad libitum* throughout the experiment.

2.5 Phytochemical Analysis of the plant (*Azadirachta indica*)

Phytochemical tests were carried out on the aqueous extracts using standard phytochemical methods as described by Evans and Trease, (1999), Sofowora (1984), Harbone (1973) and El-Olemylet al.(1994).

2.6 Induction of Diabetes

Diabetes was induced by a single intra-peritoneal injection of 60 mg/kg streptozotocin (Sigma St Louis, M.O., USA) dissolved in 0.9% normal saline to overnight fasted rats using insulin syringe. Diabetes mellitus was confirmed after the 7th day of streptozotocin treatment by the observation of fasting blood glucose (FBG)>300 mg/dl using glucometer (accu-check) [8].

2.7 Experimental Design

The animals were divided randomly into 6 groups of 5 rats each. The groups are: group 1: normal rats (control group), group 2: STZ-induced diabetic group treated with standard drug (glibenclamide), group 3: STZ-induced diabetic group untreated, group 4: STZ-induced diabetic group treated with *Azadirachta indica* leaves extract 100 mg/kg, group 5: STZ-induced diabetic group treated with *Azadirachta indica* leaves extract 300 mg/kg and group 6: STZ-induced diabetic group treated with *Azadirachta indica* leaves extract 400 mg/kg. The dose of extract was selected on the basis of the acute oral toxicity reported on the plant from the previous studies carried out by[9]. Blood glucose levels were measured before treatment and on 1st, 2nd, 4th, 6th

and 8th weeks respectively. Body weight of each animal was determined at the initiation and end of the study.

2.8 Collection of Blood Sample

After the completion of the 4 weeks treatment, the rats were fasted overnight for eight hours, anaesthetized in using chloroform and blood samples were collected from the animals through abdominal aorta into a sterile syringe. Blood samples were collected in heparinized containers and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes for separating blood plasma. The plasma obtained was pipette into labeled specimen test tubes for estimation of biochemical parameters.

2.9 Biochemical Analysis

Diagnostic kits were utilized for analyzing the biochemical parameters including Randox kits for blood glucose test, lipid profile, liver and kidney function tests, antioxidant enzyme kits for antioxidant parameters and MDA assay kits for malondialdehyde.

2.10 Data Analysis

Data obtained from the experiments were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software for windows version 21 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Duncan comparison was used to compare mean values. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

3.0 Results

Table 2: Changes in blood glucose concentrations(mg/dl) of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves during the 4 weeks treatment

Group	1 st Week	2 nd Week	3 rd Week	4 th Week
1	80.00±0.70 ^a	76.80±1.06 ^a	85.80±0.86 ^a	81.00±0.70 ^a
2	398.20±1.68 ^b	383.80±0.86 ^c	260.80±1.15 ^b	94.60±1.43 ^b
3	460.60±1.20 ^d	450.60±1.16 ^f	405.60±2.13 ^f	401.20±0.86 ^f
4	400.40±0.81 ^b	360.40±1.20 ^d	300.40±1.77 ^e	273.40±1.93 ^c
5	397.90±1.20 ^b	327.60±1.02 ^c	287.40±1.16 ^d	186.20±2.22 ^d
6	418.20±1.06 ^c	301.60±1.77 ^b	267.00±0.70 ^c	92.60±1.69 ^b

Results are Mean±SEM of 5 determinations. Values with different superscript are statistically different; values with same superscript are statistically not different at ($p < 0.05$). Group 1: normal control, Group 2: glibenclamide control, Group 3: diabetic untreated, Group 4: 100 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 5: 300 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 6: 400mg/kg leaves extract.

3.3 Liver function indices of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves

3.1 Phytochemical constituents of aqueous extract of *Azadirachta indica* leaves

Table 1 represents the phytochemical constituents of *Azadirachta indica* leaves extract.

Table 1: Phytochemical constituents of aqueous extract of *Azadirachta indica* leaves extract

Compound	Concentration
Alkaloids	+
Tannins	+
Flavonoids	+
Terpenoids	+
Phenols	+
Cardiac glycosides	+
Saponins	+

Key: (+): present

3.2 Changes in blood glucose concentrations of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves during the 4 weeks treatment

Table 2 shows the changes in blood glucose concentrations of STZ-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves during the 4 weeks treatment. There was significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in blood glucose concentrations in the diabetic group when compared with the normal control. However, administration of aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves resulted to significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in blood glucose concentrations in the treated groups when compared with the untreated. However, treatment with glibenclamide 5 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg leaves extract showed the most effective decrease when compared with other treated groups.

Liver function indices of STZ-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves is depicted in Table 3. The result showed

significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the activities of alanineaminotransferase (ALT), aspartateaminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and concentrations of total bilirubin (TB) and conjugated bilirubin (CB) and also a significant decrease in total protein (TP), albumin (ALB) and globulin (GLO) concentrations in the diabetic untreated groups when compared with the normal control. However, administration of aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves resulted to a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in the activities of ALT, AST, ALP and

concentrations of TB and CB and a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the concentrations of TP, ALB and GLO respectively when compared with diabetic untreated. Treatment with glibenclamide 5 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg showed the most effective decrease in the activities of ALT and AST and the concentrations of TB and CB and also significant increase in the concentrations of TP, ALB and GLO, whereas glibenclamide 5 mg/kg and 300 mg/kg exerted the most effective increase in the activity of ALP.

Table 3: Liver function indices of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves

Groups	ALT (μ l)	AST (μ l)	ALP (μ l)	TP (g/dl)	ALB (g/dl)	GLO (g/dl)	TB (mg/dl)	CB (mg/dl)
1.	16.20 \pm 0.37 ^a	8.00 \pm 0.44 ^a	68.00 \pm 0.70 ^a	5.90 \pm 0.07 ^a	3.98 \pm 0.08 ^a	1.92 \pm 0.09 ^a	1.24 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.12 \pm 0.02 ^a
2.	19.60 \pm 0.40 ^b	9.60 \pm 0.24 ^b	80.80 \pm 0.58 ^b	5.70 \pm 0.07 ^c	4.00 \pm 0.07 ^a	1.70 \pm 0.08 ^{a,c,d}	1.54 \pm 0.02 ^b	0.18 \pm 0.03 ^a
3.	89.40 \pm 0.50 ^f	100.80 \pm 0.37 ^e	217.00 \pm 0.44 ^f	1.76 \pm 0.05 ^e	1.68 \pm 0.08 ^c	0.20 \pm 0.03 ^c	8.28 \pm 0.13 ^f	1.50 \pm 0.03 ^c
4.	39.60 \pm 0.40 ^c	41.20 \pm 0.37 ^d	140.20 \pm 0.58 ^c	4.04 \pm 0.09 ^b	3.62 \pm 0.08 ^b	0.52 \pm 0.09 ^{b,c}	2.56 \pm 0.05 ^c	0.40 \pm 0.03 ^c
5.	28.40 \pm 0.67 ^d	15.00 \pm 0.31 ^c	85.60 \pm 1.96 ^c	4.74 \pm 0.06 ^c	3.92 \pm 0.04 ^a	0.82 \pm 0.07 ^b	2.02 \pm 0.09 ^d	0.20 \pm 0.03 ^b
6.	21.60 \pm 0.50 ^c	10.60 \pm 0.24 ^b	89.00 \pm 0.31 ^d	6.20 \pm 0.21 ^a	4.26 \pm 0.05 ^d	1.94 \pm 0.25 ^a	1.82 \pm 0.03 ^c	0.14 \pm 0.02 ^a

Results are Mean \pm SEM of 5 determinations. Values with different superscript are statistically different and values with same superscript are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$). Key: ALT: Alanine amino transferase, AST: Aspartate amino transferase, ALP: Alkaline phosphatase, TP: Total protein, ALB: Albumin, GLO: Globulin, TB: Total bilirubin, CB: Conjugated bilirubin. Group 1: normal control, Group 2: glibenclamide control, Group 3: diabetic untreated, Group 4: 100 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 5: 300 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 6: 400 mg/kg leaves extract.

3.4 Urea and creatinine concentrations of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves

Table 4 represents urea and creatinine concentrations of STZ-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves. The result showed significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in urea and creatinine concentrations in the diabetic groups when compared with the normal control. However, administration aqueous extract of *A. indica* resulted to significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in the urea and creatinine concentrations in the treated groups when compared with the diabetic untreated. However, treatment with glibenclamide 5 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg leaves extract exhibited the most effective decrease in urea and creatinine concentrations among the treated groups.

Table 4: Urea and creatinine concentrations of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves

Groups	Urea (mmol/l)	Creatinine (μ mol/l)
1.	4.52 \pm 0.05 ^a	51.40 \pm 0.50 ^a
2.	4.96 \pm 0.09 ^b	57.80 \pm 0.37 ^b
3.	11.94 \pm 0.07 ^f	279.00 \pm 0.70 ^f
4.	8.98 \pm 0.03 ^c	155.00 \pm 0.40 ^c
5.	6.92 \pm 0.05 ^d	110.00 \pm 0.31 ^d
6.	5.64 \pm 0.09 ^c	78.00 \pm 0.31 ^c

Results are Mean \pm SEM of 5 determinations. Values with different superscript are statistically different and values with same superscript are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$). Group 1: normal control, Group 2: glibenclamide control, Group 3: diabetic untreated, Group 4: 100 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 5: 300 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 6: 400 mg/kg leaves extract.

3.5 Antioxidant parameters of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves

Table 5 shows antioxidant parameters of STZ-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves. The result indicated significant

decrease ($p < 0.05$) in the activities of antioxidant enzymes and glutathione (GSH) and a significant increase in Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration in diabetic untreated when compared with the normal control. Administration of aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves resulted to significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the activities of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and

the concentration of GSH in the treated groups when compared with the diabetic untreated. However, treatment with 300 mg/kg leaves extract and 400 mg/kg leaves extract exhibited the most effective increase in the activities of SOD, CAT and the concentration of GSH and also the most effective decrease in the concentration of MDA among treated groups.

Table 5: Antioxidant parameters of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves

Groups	SOD (μml)	CAT (μml)	GSH (μml)	MDA (nmol/ml)
1	26.84 \pm 0.60 ^a	15.04 \pm 0.27 ^a	17.76 \pm 0.38 ^a	99.10 \pm 0.12 ^a
2	21.90 \pm 0.57 ^c	11.96 \pm 0.20 ^c	14.84 \pm 0.22 ^c	117.96 \pm 0.23 ^d
3	18.00 \pm 0.72 ^b	7.64 \pm 0.16 ^c	8.60 \pm 0.29 ^c	140.26 \pm 0.16 ^f
4	17.24 \pm 0.55 ^c	11.22 \pm 1.42 ^b	11.98 \pm 0.25 ^b	121.00 \pm 0.35 ^e
5	24.72 \pm 0.19 ^d	13.26 \pm 0.11 ^d	16.34 \pm 1.50 ^d	101.12 \pm 1.99 ^c
6	29.40 \pm 0.33 ^f	17.16 \pm 0.16 ^f	22.08 \pm 0.25 ^f	78.46 \pm 0.11 ^b

Results are Mean \pm SEM of 5 determinations. Values with different superscript are statistically different and values with same superscript are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$). Key: SOD: Superoxide dismutase, CAT: Catalase, GSH: Reduced glutathione and MDA: Malondialdehyde. Group 1: normal control, Group 2: glibenclamide control, Group 3: diabetic untreated, Group 4: 100 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 5: 300 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 6: 400 mg/kg leaves extract.

3.6 Lipid profile of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves

Table 6 shows total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high density lipoprotein (HDL), low density lipoprotein (LDL) and atherogenic index (AI) concentrations of STZ-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *A. indica* leaves. The result indicated significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in TC, TG, LDL and AI concentrations and a significant decrease in HDL concentration in diabetic untreated when compared with the normal control. Administration of aqueous extract

A. indica leaves resulted to significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in TC, TG, LDL and AI and a significant increase in HDL concentration in the treated groups when compared with the diabetic untreated. Treatment with 100 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg leave extract showed the most significant decrease in TC. Similarly, treatment with glibenclamide 5 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg leaves extract was observed to have the most effective decrease in TG, LDL and AI respectively among the treated groups. Also, treatment with glibenclamide 5 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg resulted to most sufficient increase in HDL concentration among treated groups.

Table 6: Lipid profile of streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats administered aqueous extract *Azadirachta indica* leaves and stem-bark

Group	TC (mmol/l)	TG (mmol/l)	HDL (mmol/l)	LDL (mmol/l)	AI
1	3.72 \pm 0.05 ^a	1.84 \pm 0.04 ^a	1.20 \pm 0.03 ^a	2.28 \pm 0.03 ^a	1.90 \pm 0.02 ^a
2	5.34 \pm 0.02 ^d	1.78 \pm 0.03 ^a	2.52 \pm 0.02 ^g	2.26 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.03 \pm 0.01 ^a
3	8.18 \pm 0.03 ^c	6.40 \pm 0.03 ^c	0.36 \pm 0.02 ^d	7.46 \pm 0.02 ^f	21.13 \pm 1.51 ^d
4	5.26 \pm 0.04 ^{c,d}	3.62 \pm 0.03 ^d	0.98 \pm 0.03 ^{b,c}	4.00 \pm 0.03 ^c	4.10 \pm 0.15 ^c
5	4.58 \pm 0.03 ^b	2.20 \pm 0.03 ^c	1.30 \pm 0.03 ^c	3.10 \pm 0.03 ^d	2.39 \pm 0.07 ^{a,b}
6	5.14 \pm 0.06 ^c	2.10 \pm 0.03 ^b	2.10 \pm 0.04 ^f	2.74 \pm 0.04 ^c	1.30 \pm 0.03 ^a

Results are Mean \pm SEM of 5 determinations. Values with different superscript are statistically different and values with same superscript are not statistically different at ($p < 0.05$). Key: TC: Total cholesterol, TG: triglycerides, HDL: High density lipoprotein, LDL: Low density lipoprotein and AI: Atherogenic index. Group 1: normal control, Group 2: glibenclamide control, Group 3: diabetic untreated, Group 4: 100 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 5: 300 mg/kg leaves extract, Group 6: 400mg/kg leaves extract.

4.0 Discussion

Herbal therapy remains the safest, accessible and affordable which people relied for the treatment of various ailments and such plants include *Azadirachta indica* [10]. *A. indica* is widely utilized for its health benefits since time immemorial. All parts of this plant are important in traditional system of medicines[11]. Leaves extract of *A. indica* is used in the treatment of various diseases, among which is diabetes mellitus. The phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, phenols, cardiac glycosides and saponins. These phytochemicals were believed to be responsible for the antidiabetic property of *A. indica* leaves extract. Result of phytochemical analysis is in line with the findings of Tiwari et al. [11]. The results also agrees with the findings of Rania et al.[12] who reported the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavanoids, terpenoids and saponins in the leaves extract. The phytochemical findings is also corresponds with the result reported by Mamta et al. [13]. The aqueous extract of *A. indica* leaves reduced the concentration fasting blood glucose significantly ($p < 0.05$) towards recovery. This indicated that the extract has similar effect as the conventional drug used for the treatment of diabetes and can be used as a hypoglycemic agent even at a dose of 300 mg/kg. This result agrees with the findings of Tiwari et al. [11, 14, 15]. Rania et al.[12] reported hypoglycemic property of *A. indica* leaves extract in alloxan-induced diabetic rats which corresponds to the findings from this study. It was reported that the *A. indica* is very effective in maintenance of blood glucose concentration and also good in preventing and delaying the onset of diabetes [12]. The result also agrees with the findings by Ezeigwe and Francis, [16] who revealed that leaves extract of *A. indica* significantly decreased blood glucose levels in STZ-induced diabetic rats. Ezeigwe and Francis, [16]reported that leaves extract of *A. indica* inhibited α -amylase enzyme which is one of the key enzymes in carbohydrate metabolism. The reduction in the concentration of blood glucose can be due to the presence of the phytochemicals; alkaloids, tannins, flavanoids, terpenoids, phenols, cardiac glycosides and saponins. Alkaloids were reported to inhibit the enzyme α -glucosidase [12]. Terpenes reported to reduce glucagon secretion and helps in taking of physiologically important elements such as Cu^{2+} and Mg^{2+} for beta cells functions[17]. Furthermore, the antidiabetic effect of flavonoids is evident as they

inhibit the enzyme aldose reductase that catalyzes the conversion of glucose to sorbitol, which contributes to complications of diabetes [12]. Saponins have been reported to cause hypoglycemia [10].

Furthermore, the extract also significantly increased the activities of antioxidant enzymes (SOD and CAT) and GSH concentration. This indicates that oxidative stress caused by STZ could be reversed due to the effect of leaves extract. Free radical-scavenging activities of the tannins and phenolics which give rise to fairly stable radical suggest that they may be responsible for the antidiabetic activity of leaves extract[10].This result is in agreement with the reports by Hossain et al. [18] who revealed the free radical scavenging potentials of *A. indica* leaves due to rich source of vital antioxidants. Rania et al.[12] reported antioxidant potential of *A. indica* leaves extract in alloxan-induced diabetic rats which conforms to the findings from this work. The significant decreased in MDA level was also observed by the extract which could be attributed to the presence of flavonoids, phenols and tannins having antioxidant activity. The findings corresponds with the reports by Ezeigwe et al. [10] who reported significant reduction MDA level in STZ-induced diabetic rats after treatment with *A. indica* leaves extract. It also conforms to a report by Abubakar et al. [19] who reported that oral administration of aqueous leaves extract of *A. indica* significantly decreased MDA levels in diabetic rats. The phytochemicals might be responsible for the lipid peroxidation inhibition by scavenging free radicals [20].

The extract significantly decreased lipid profile (TC, TG and LDL) and significantly increased HDL level. This could be due the presence of saponins, flavonoids and other phytochemicals. Saponins are known to lower TG levels due to its lytic role and it is established that VLDL cholesterol is the main transporter of TG in the serum and are capable of precipitating anterohepatic circulation of bile acid, making it unavailable for intestinal absorption thus decreasing cholesterol levels [21]. This finding is in agreement with Ezeigwe et al. who reported significant decrease in TC, TG and LDL and significant increase in HDL in STZ-induced diabetic rats treated with *A. indica* leaves extract. It is also in line with a study reported by Chattopadhyay and Bandyopadhyay [22] and the hypolipidemic potential of the extract could prevent the progression of atherosclerosis [22,

23]. Furthermore, it also corresponds to the findings by Shradha and Sisodia [24] who reported hypolipidemic property of ethanolic leaves extract of *A. indica* in STZ-induced diabetic rats. Similarly, the result also conforms to the findings by Adel et al. [23] who reported significant decrease in TC, TG, LDL and significant increase in HDL in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. However, the result also corresponds to a study by Srivastava et al. [25] who reported significant decrease in lipid profile and a significant increase in HDL. Meanwhile, this study disagrees with Usharani et al. [26] who reported no significant difference in the hypolipidemic effect of *A. indica* leaves on human subjects. The extract also significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased the activities of AST, ALT and ALP and the concentrations of total protein and albumin. This Finding is in line with a study by Ezeigwe and Francis, [16] who reported significant decrease in the activities of AST, ALT and ALP in STZ-induced diabetic rats treated with *A. indica* leaves extract. It has also conforms to a study by Srivastava et al. [25] who revealed significant decrease in the activities of AST and ALT in STZ-induced diabetic rats by chloroform leaves extract of *A. indica*. The result also is in line with study reported by Bharali et al. [27] that revealed significant decrease in the activities of ALT, AST and ALP and the level of serum bilirubin, also reported significant increase in total protein and albumin levels in STZ-induced diabetic Wistar rats treated with *A. indica* leaves extract for 30 days which is in line with the findings of this study. The result also conforms to the findings by Adel et al. [23] that reported significant decrease in the activities of AST, ALT and ALP in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. The hepatoprotective potentials of the extract could be due the presence of flavanoids and terpenoids [28] which exert their action either through improving hepatic glucose metabolism, restoring antioxidant defense, or limiting inflammatory responses [29].

The extract also significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased the concentrations of urea and creatinine. This could be due to the presence of flavonoids and phenols which have the ability to reverse inflammation, improve hepatocyte lipid metabolism or regulate glucose which through preventing the action of epinephrine on glycogenolysis and the utilization of peripheral glucose and [30, 31]. This study is in line with findings by Ezeigwe and Francis, [16] and Sonia et al. [27] who reported significant decrease in the concentrations of urea and creatinine in STZ-

induced diabetic rats treated with *A. indica* leaves extract. It also agrees with a finding by Srivastava et al. [25] who reported significant decrease in the concentrations of urea and creatinine in STZ-induced diabetic rats by chloroform leaves extract of *A. indica*. Similarly, it also conforms to the findings of Adel et al. [23] who reported significant decrease in the concentrations of urea and creatinine in alloxan-induced diabetic rats.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicated that aqueous leaves extract of *A. indica* normalized blood glucose, liver, kidney and antioxidant parameters and lipid profile respectively. The extract is effective in the management of diabetes and can closely be compared with the glibenclamide. This indicated that *A. indica* is a reservoir of phytochemistry and can serve as a good source of diabetic drug discovery.

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